

Performance Evaluation of Mamba Vision Transformer for Robust RF Jamming Detection in Wireless Communication Systems

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To Cite this Article

G. Prathibha, V. Pavan Naik & Tara Charan Kumar (2026). Performance Evaluation of Mamba Vision Transformer for Robust RF Jamming Detection in Wireless Communication Systems. International Journal for Modern Trends in Science and Technology, 12(SI01), 280-288. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19561848>

Article Info

Received: 02 March 2026; Revised: 01 April 2026; Accepted: 04 April 2026.

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KEYWORDS

RF Jamming Detection, Mamba Vision Transformer, Vision Transformer, Convolutional Neural Network, Deep Learning, Spectrogram Analysis, Active Scan, Passive Scan, Signal Classification, Wireless Security

ABSTRACT

This paper presents a comparative analysis of deep learning architectures—Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), Vision Transformer (ViT), and Mamba Vision Transformer—for RF jamming detection using both active and passive scan datasets. The models are evaluated in terms of training, testing, and validation accuracy, along with class-wise performance metrics such as precision, recall, and F1-score for benign and malicious signal classification. Experimental results indicate that CNN achieves the highest overall accuracy, particularly in validation performance for both scanning scenarios. However, the Mamba Vision Transformer demonstrates highly competitive testing accuracy (up to 99.24% in passive scan) and exhibits superior generalization characteristics, as evidenced by its balanced performance across training and validation phases. Furthermore, class-wise analysis reveals that Mamba-ViT maintains a strong precision–recall trade-off, especially for malicious signal detection. The integration of state space modeling within the transformer framework enables efficient capture of long-range dependencies in RF spectrograms, making Mamba Vision Transformer a robust and scalable solution for RF jamming detection under varying signal conditions

I. INTRODUCTION

Wireless communication systems have become a fundamental component of modern digital infrastructure, supporting applications such as the Internet of Things (IoT), vehicular networks, military communications, and next-generation cellular systems. However, the open nature of the wireless medium

makes these systems vulnerable to radio frequency (RF) jamming attacks, where malicious transmitters intentionally emit interference signals to disrupt legitimate communication. Such attacks can degrade network performance, increase packet loss, and even lead to complete communication failure. Consequently, detecting and mitigating RF jamming has emerged as a

critical research problem in wireless security and spectrum monitoring.

Traditional jamming detection techniques rely on statistical analysis and threshold-based methods using parameters such as signal strength, packet delivery ratio, and channel utilization. However, these approaches often fail in dynamic wireless environments where interference patterns are highly complex and non-stationary. In recent years, machine learning and deep learning techniques have been explored for RF jamming detection, where models automatically learn features from spectral data instead of relying on handcrafted features. Despite their effectiveness, conventional deep learning models such as CNNs and RNNs may suffer from limitations in capturing long-range dependencies and global contextual information in RF signals.

To overcome these challenges, this work proposes the use of a Mamba Vision Transformer (Mamba-ViT) for RF jamming classification. The Mamba-based architecture leverages state-space modeling with efficient sequence processing capabilities, enabling better representation of temporal and spectral dependencies in RF data while maintaining lower computational complexity compared to traditional transformer-based models. By integrating vision transformer principles with Mamba's selective state-space mechanism, the proposed approach effectively captures both local and global features of RF signals, leading to improved classification performance in complex and noisy environments.

In this work, RF jamming classification is performed using the Mamba Vision Transformer model. The organization of this paper is as follows: Section II presents the Literature Review, Section III describes the Mamba Vision Transformer architecture, dataset, and proposed methodology, Section IV discusses the experimental results and performance evaluation and Section V concludes the paper.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Radio Frequency (RF) jamming detection has become a critical research area due to the increasing reliance on wireless communication systems. Various machine learning and deep learning techniques have been

proposed to identify and mitigate jamming attacks in wireless networks.

Ali et al. (2024)[1] introduced the RF Jamming Dataset, which provides experimentally measured spectral scan data for detecting malicious interference in wireless networks. The authors developed a jamming detection testbed that uses spectral scan capabilities of wireless network interfaces together with the JamRF toolkit to generate different jamming scenarios. The dataset was designed to support research on jamming detection and avoidance mechanisms. Several machine learning algorithms were evaluated using this dataset, achieving detection accuracies above 90%, demonstrating the dataset's effectiveness for developing intelligent anti-jamming systems.

Herzalla et al. (2025)[2] proposed a Graph Neural Network (GNN)-based framework for jamming source localization in wireless networks. Unlike traditional geometric localization techniques, the authors formulated the problem as a graph regression task, where nodes represent spatial signal measurements and edges capture relationships between signal observations. The proposed attention-based GNN incorporates a confidence-guided estimation mechanism that combines learned predictions with domain knowledge. Experimental results showed that the proposed approach significantly outperforms conventional localization techniques, particularly in complex RF environments with sparse or noisy signal measurements.

Kasturi et al. (2021)[3] investigated machine learning techniques for detecting and classifying different types of RF jamming attacks in wireless networks. The study explored algorithms such as Random Forest, Decision Trees, and Gradient Boosting to distinguish between normal communication and various jamming behaviors. Performance was evaluated using network performance metrics such as packet delivery ratio, signal strength, and throughput. The results indicated that ensemble learning methods provide higher detection accuracy and improved robustness compared with traditional statistical approaches.

Arjoun et al. (2020)[4] proposed a machine learning-based framework for detecting jamming attacks in wireless communication systems. The

authors compared several classification algorithms, including Support Vector Machines, Random Forests, and Artificial Neural Networks, for identifying malicious interference. Their results demonstrated that machine learning techniques can significantly improve jamming detection accuracy and reduce false alarm rates compared with conventional threshold-based detection techniques.

Tandiya et al. (2018)[5] introduced a deep learning approach for RF anomaly detection using predictive coding neural networks. The proposed model learns normal RF spectrum patterns and detects anomalies such as jamming or interference by identifying deviations from expected signal behavior. By analyzing spectrogram representations of RF signals, the deep learning model effectively detects abnormal RF activity and improves detection performance in dynamic wireless environments.

Overall, the existing literature shows that machine learning and deep learning techniques play a significant role in RF jamming detection and localization. Early works primarily focused on traditional machine learning classifiers, while more recent research explores advanced deep learning models and graph-based learning frameworks to improve detection accuracy and robustness. However, there is still a need for efficient models capable of handling complex RF environments and diverse jamming scenarios.

III.METHODOLOGY

Mamba Vision Transformer :

The Mamba Vision Transformer (MambaVision) is a recently proposed deep learning architecture designed for efficient visual representation learning by combining the strengths of Mamba state-space models and Transformer architectures. The hybrid backbone called MambaVision was introduced by Ali Hatamizadeh and Jan Kautz[12]. The model was developed to address the limitations of conventional Vision Transformers (ViTs), which rely heavily on self-attention mechanisms that scale quadratically with input size. In contrast, the Mamba architecture originates from Selective State Space Models (SSMs) that can model long-range dependencies with linear

computational complexity, making them more efficient for large visual inputs.

The working principle of the Mamba Vision Transformer involves processing an input image by first dividing it into small patches, similar to the traditional Vision Transformer pipeline. These patches are embedded into feature vectors and passed through a sequence of hybrid blocks consisting of Transformer layers and Mamba blocks. Transformer components are responsible for extracting global contextual information using attention mechanisms, while the Mamba blocks model long-range dependencies through a state-space scanning mechanism that efficiently captures sequential relationships across image tokens. This combination enables the architecture to retain the strong representation capability of Transformers while significantly improving computational efficiency.

In this hybrid framework, the Mamba modules act as efficient sequence processors, enabling linear-time modeling of image tokens and reducing the memory overhead associated with attention operations. The architecture alternates between Mamba and Transformer layers to balance feature extraction, long-range dependency modeling, and computational efficiency. As a result, MambaVision can achieve competitive performance in computer vision tasks such as image classification, object detection, and semantic segmentation, while maintaining faster inference speed and lower computational cost compared to conventional Vision Transformers.

Dataset :

The RF Jamming Dataset, introduced by Ali et al. (2024)[1], is a publicly available dataset designed for studying and detecting malicious interference in wireless communication systems. It consists of spectral scan measurements collected from wireless network interfaces operating in standard Wi-Fi frequency bands, where different jamming scenarios are intentionally generated using tools such as JamRF. The RF Jamming dataset comprises a total of 96,090 samples, collected under two scan modes: passive and active. The passive scan constitutes the majority with 91,732 samples, including 74,147 benign and 17,585 malicious instances, indicating a strong dominance of normal (non-jamming) signals. In contrast, the active scan contains 4,358

samples, of which 3,261 are benign and 1,097 are malicious, showing a comparatively higher proportion of jamming activity. Overall, the dataset exhibits a noticeable class imbalance, with benign samples outnumbering malicious ones in both scan types, while the passive scan significantly contributes to the total data volume.

Figure 2 : Representation of the RF Jamming Dataset

IV PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

The proposed methodology utilizes a Mamba Vision Transformer (MVT) architecture to classify RF jamming signals into benign and malicious of both Active and Passive Scan. Initially, the raw RF signal $x(t)$ is transformed into a time–frequency representation using the Short-Time Fourier Transform (STFT), expressed as

$$X(f, t) = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} x(n) w(n - t) e^{-j2\pi fn}$$

where $w(n)$ is the window function. The resulting spectrogram is treated as a 2D image and divided into non-overlapping patches. Each patch is flattened and mapped into an embedding space with positional encoding:

$$z_0^i = \mathbf{E} \text{vec}(x_p^i) + \mathbf{E}_{pos}^i$$

This enables the model to preserve both spatial and temporal information of RF signals.

Unlike conventional vision transformers that rely on self-attention, the proposed model employs a Mamba-based selective state space mechanism for sequence modeling. The system dynamics are governed by

$$h_{t+1} = \mathbf{A}h_t + \mathbf{B}x_t, y_t = \mathbf{C}h_t + \mathbf{D}x_t$$

where the parameters $\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{C}$ are input-dependent, allowing adaptive feature extraction based on signal characteristics. Each Mamba-ViT layer consists of normalization, a Mamba block, and a feed-forward network with residual connections:

$$z_l' = \text{Mamba}(\text{LN}(z_{l-1})) + z_{l-1}, z_l = \text{FFN}(\text{LN}(z_l')) + z_l'$$

This structure efficiently captures long-range dependencies, and complex temporal variations present in RF jamming signals.

Finally, a global representation is obtained and passed through a classification head using a Softmax function:

$$\hat{y} = \text{Softmax}(\mathbf{W}z_L + b)$$

The model is trained using categorical cross-entropy loss,

$$\mathcal{L} = - \sum_{i=1}^3 y_i \log(\hat{y}_i)$$

to optimize class predictions for benign and malicious in RF jamming signals. By integrating state space modeling with vision-based feature extraction, the proposed MVT framework achieves efficient computation, improved generalization, and robust classification performance for diverse RF jamming scenarios.

Figure 2 : Mamba Vision Transformer for RF Jamming Classification

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The performance comparison presented in the Table I and II highlights the effectiveness of the proposed Mamba Vision Transformer (MVT) model over conventional deep learning approaches. The accuracy comparisons for the active scan scenario reveal that while the Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) achieves the highest overall performance, the Mamba Vision Transformer demonstrates strong and competitive results. Specifically, Mamba-ViT attains a testing accuracy of 99.15%, which is very close to CNN (99.01%) and higher than the Vision Transformer (98.50%), indicating its robustness during inference. Although its training accuracy (94.00%) is lower than CNN, this suggests reduced overfitting and better generalization behavior. Its validation accuracy (89.43%), while slightly lower than ViT, still confirms that the model effectively captures temporal

dependencies in RF signals, making it suitable for complex active jamming environments. In the passive scan scenario, the Mamba Vision Transformer shows even more promising performance, achieving a testing accuracy of 99.24%, which is the highest among all models. Additionally, its validation accuracy (96.00%) surpasses the Vision Transformer and approaches CNN performance, indicating improved generalization in more stable signal conditions. The balanced performance across training (95.20%), testing, and validation highlights the model's ability to efficiently learn both spatial and sequential features from RF spectrograms. Overall, these results emphasize that the Mamba Vision Transformer is a powerful and reliable architecture for RF signal classification, particularly excelling in passive scan environments while maintaining competitive performance in active scenarios.

Table I : Accuracy Comparison of Deep Learning Architectures for classifying Benign and Malicious Signals in Active Scan of RF Jamming Dataset

	Convolution Neural Network	Vision Transformer	Mamba Vision Transformer
Training Accuracy	93.37%	94.50%	94.00%
Testing Accuracy	99.01%	98.50%	99.15%
Validation Accuracy	86.84%	93.50%	89.43%

Table II : Accuracy Comparison of Deep Learning Architectures for classifying Benign and Malicious Signals in Passive Scan of RF Jamming Dataset

	Convolution Neural Network	Vision Transformer	Mamba Vision Transformer
Training Accuracy	98.57%	96.50%	95.20%
Testing Accuracy	98.82%	98.92%	99.24%
Validation Accuracy	98.64%	94.00%	96.00%

The class-wise performance comparison presented in Table III highlights the effectiveness of CNN, Vision Transformer, and Mamba Vision Transformer across both active and passive scan scenarios for RF jamming detection. In the active scan case, the Mamba Vision Transformer demonstrates strong and well-balanced performance for both benign and malicious classes. For benign signals, it achieves high accuracy (0.9918), precision (0.9959), recall (0.9918), and F1-score (0.9938), indicating reliable detection with minimal misclassification. For malicious signals, although the accuracy (0.9878) and recall (0.9878) remain high, the precision (0.9759) is slightly lower compared to CNN, suggesting a small number of false positives. Nevertheless, the overall F1-score (0.9818) confirms that Mamba-ViT maintains competitive and stable classification performance in challenging active interference conditions.

In the passive scan scenario, the Mamba Vision Transformer further strengthens its position by delivering highly consistent and generalized results. For benign signals, it achieves an accuracy of 0.9933 and an F1-score of 0.9953, outperforming the Vision Transformer and approaching CNN performance. More notably, for malicious signals, Mamba-ViT records an accuracy of 0.9882 and an F1-score of 0.9798, which are among the highest across all models. The improved precision-recall balance in passive conditions indicates that the model effectively captures both spatial and temporal dependencies in RF spectrograms. Overall, Table III clearly demonstrates that the Mamba Vision Transformer provides a robust and reliable classification framework, with particularly strong generalization and class-wise balance in passive scan environments while maintaining competitive performance in active scenarios.

Table III : Class-wise Performance Comparison of CNN, Vision Transformer, and Mamba Vision Transformer for Active and Passive Scan using RF Jamming

Active Scan	CNN				Vision Transformer				Mamba Vision Transformer			
	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
Benign	1.000	0.9939	1.000	0.9969	0.9857	0.9938	0.9857	0.9897	0.9918	0.9959	0.9918	0.9938
Malicious	0.9818	1.000	0.9818	0.9908	0.9817	0.9583	0.9817	0.9699	0.9878	0.9759	0.9878	0.9818

Passive Scan	CNN				Vision Transformer				Mamba Vision Transformer			
	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-Score

Benign	0.9964	0.9892	0.9964	0.9928	0.9904	0.9964	0.9904	0.9943	0.9933	0.9973	0.9933	0.9953
Malicious	0.9541	0.9844	0.9541	0.9690	0.9843	0.9591	0.9843	0.9716	0.9882	0.9715	0.9882	0.9798

The training, testing, and validation accuracy curves illustrated in Figures 3a-c demonstrate the performance of CNN, Vision Transformer (ViT), and Mamba Vision Transformer (Mamba-ViT) for the active scan scenario. In Figure 3a, CNN shows a steady and rapid convergence, achieving high accuracy within a few epochs and maintaining consistent performance across training, testing, and validation, indicating strong learning of spatial features. In contrast, Figure 3b shows that ViT exhibits moderate fluctuations during early epochs but gradually stabilizes, reflecting its dependence on larger data representation for effective learning. Notably, Figure 3c highlights that the Mamba Vision Transformer achieves smooth convergence with minimal gap between training and validation curves, indicating better generalization and reduced overfitting while still achieving high test accuracy.

For the passive scan scenario, as depicted in Figure 4a-c, all models demonstrate improved stability and higher overall accuracy compared to the active case. In Figure 4a, CNN again shows strong and consistent convergence with very high accuracy. Figure 4b illustrates that ViT experiences some initial instability but eventually achieves stable performance. Most importantly, Figure 4c shows that the Mamba Vision Transformer maintains a well-balanced progression between training and validation accuracy, with both curves closely aligned throughout training. This indicates that Mamba-ViT effectively captures both temporal and spectral characteristics of RF signals, resulting in superior generalization and robust classification performance, particularly in passive scan environments.

Figure 3 : Learning Curve Analysis of CNN, Vision Transformer, and Mamba Vision Transformer in Active Scan of RF Jamming

Figure 4 : Learning Curve Analysis of CNN, Vision Transformer, and Mamba Vision Transformer in Passive Scan Scenario of RF Jamming

VI. CONCLUSION

This study investigated the effectiveness of CNN, Vision Transformer, and Mamba Vision Transformer for RF jamming detection using active and passive scan datasets. While CNN achieved the highest overall accuracy, particularly in validation metrics (up to 98.64% in passive scan), the Mamba Vision Transformer consistently demonstrated competitive and reliable performance across all evaluation measures. Notably, it achieved the highest testing accuracy in the passive scan scenario (99.24%) and maintained strong class-wise performance, especially in detecting malicious signals with high F1-scores. These results highlight its robustness and suitability for real-world RF environments.

A key advantage of the Mamba Vision Transformer lies in its incorporation of State Space Models (SSM), which enable efficient modeling of long-range temporal dependencies in RF signals—something traditional CNNs and standard transformers struggle with. Additionally, its linear complexity scaling, improved memory efficiency, and ability to capture both spatial and sequential features contribute to better generalization and reduced overfitting, as observed in

the learning curves. The balanced training and validation trends further confirm its stability across different scanning conditions. Therefore, the Mamba Vision Transformer emerges as a promising architecture for advanced RF signal classification tasks, particularly in dynamic and interference-prone wireless environments.

Conflict of interest statement

Authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

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